

Project Psyche Code of Conduct

Version history:

- Document created 8th October 2025

All genomes that are generated by Project Psyche are made publicly accessible to use. The Project Psyche community jointly developed the following guidelines for publishing work that uses varying numbers of Project Psyche genomes to acknowledge the contributions of the community.

To facilitate the coordinated analysis of the first 1000 lepidopteran genomes, the Project Psyche community are forming working groups. Everyone is welcome to suggest analyses and to contribute to making exciting findings with the genomes.

We also aim to establish best practice guidelines and standards for sampling, data analysis and collaborative research. To get involved, sign up to our mailing list and share your ideas at our next meeting. Sign up here: tinyurl.com/projectpsyche.

Publishing code of conduct for Phase I and II of Project Psyche:

- **< 10 genomes:** Cite the relevant Genome Notes and relevant Darwin Tree of Life whitepaper (Darwin Tree of Life Project Consortium, The Darwin Tree et al. 2022), and the upcoming Psyche whitepaper (Wright et al. 2025). Please also mention the Project Psyche Community in the Acknowledgements.
- **< 100 genomes:** Tell the Psyche community early on (10 minutes in a monthly meeting), cite the relevant whitepapers, cite the Genome Notes in a Supplementary Table.
- **>100 genomes:** Tell the Psyche community early on (10 minutes in a monthly meeting), add the 'Project Psyche community' collective author as co-author and cite the relevant whitepapers.

References

- Darwin Tree of Life Project Consortium, The Darwin Tree, Mark Blaxter, Nova Mieszkowska, Federica Di Palma, Peter Holland, Richard Durbin, Thomas Richards, et al. 2022. "Sequence Locally, Think Globally: The Darwin Tree of Life Project." *Proceedings of the National Academy of Sciences* 119 (4): e2115642118.
- Wright, Charlotte J., Niklas Wahlberg, Roger Vila, Marko Mutanen, Pável Matos-Maraví, Kay Lucek, Irena Kleckova, et al. 2025. "Project Psyche: Generating and Utilising Reference Genomes for All Lepidoptera in Europe." *EcoEvoRxiv*. September 10, 2025. <https://ecoevorxiv.org/repository/view/9760/>.